

Coupling GB-SAR and visual photography for 3D modelling of an Alpine glacier surface kinematics

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We present the coupling of the results of a survey campaign collecting data simultaneously from two different and independent remote sensing monitoring devices observing the surface deformation of the Planpincieux glacier, on the Italian side of the Mont Blanc massif, to the aim of 3-dimensional modelling the glacier kinematics. The campaign lasted 25 days and occurred in correspondence of the beginning of the Alpine cold season. During the measurements rainfall and snowfall events occurred.

The considered devices are a low-cost optical photography station (OPS) and a ground-based synthetic aperture radar (GB-SAR).

The OPS was placed almost in front of the glacier and measured daily motion components orthogonal to the line of sight (LOS). The processing is performed through spatial cross-correlation between consecutive images, acquired at the same hours to limit shadow effects. The images are orthorectified on a 1 m-resolution digital surface model (DSM) of the glacier and a pixel-to-metric conversion is performed.

The GB-SAR acquired data every 16 minutes. It measured the motion component parallel to the LOS, which is almost parallel to the glacier mean slope. The main processing steps include i) a coherence-driven pixel-selection criterion to identify glacier areas, ii) 2D unwrapping algorithm, iii) atmosphere phase screen (APS) filtering with a newly 2D polynomial model, function of the elevation. The radar maps are also georeferenced on the DSM.

Finally, from the 3 different components of the glacier surface motion it is possible to reconstruct the actual deformation vector. The results are mapped at 1 m-resolution.

The results show that the motion vectors follow the maximum gradient direction but with a more slanted angle, suggesting a non-laminar flow of the glacier with a complex kinematics that comprehends sliding, ice deformation and creeping processes.